

A Systematic Review on the Existing CNN-based Techniques for Detection and Classification of Brain Tumor in MRI Images (2020-2025)

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ABSTRACT

Automated brain tumor detection and classification of magnetic resonance images is a challenging task. One of the most widely used method in the recent years for these tasks include deep learning-based techniques particularly, CNNs-based techniques which have emerged as powerful method for handling complex biomedical data. The main objective of this study is to carry out a systematic and comprehensive review along with their critical analysis of the studies that have used deep CNN-based techniques for brain tumor detection and classification in MRI images in the past six years 2020 and 2025. A rigorous search of databases including PubMed, ScienceDirect, Google Scholar, and IEEE Access and other databases identified 310 articles, from which 50 articles with high quality were selected for analysis. The key findings of this study presented by charts, graphs, and tables to facilitate a better understanding of the effectiveness of CNN-based techniques in brain tumor detection and classification for future researchers..

Keywords: Deep Learning, CNN, Brain tumor, Detection, Classification, MRI.

INTRODUCTION

The brain is an important organ in human body which responsible for processing billion cells, controlling all other organ's function [1]. When these cells growth abnormally, they create form of tumor, impact on the cell's activities and threat human life [2]. They come in different types, progression and treatment response so accurate and timely diagnosis is needed for intervention. Brain tumors are classified into primary and secondary. Primary types include gliomas, meningiomas and pituitary, each with its own characteristics. Early detection and classification of these tumors are important in determining treatment and improving patient outcome. But because of the complexity and variability of brain tumors accurate diagnosis is a big challenge in clinical practice [3,4]. Magnetic resonance imaging or MRI is a non-invasive and effective method for diagnosing and assessing the response to intraoperative treatment of brain tumors [5], which provides information about the brain tissue and brain tumor by providing soft tissue contrast. It is considered a standard method for the diagnosis and

treatment of brain tumors. It is used in combination with T1-weighted, T2-weighted and contrast-enhanced MRI [6].

Brain tumor detection methods using MRI images include segmentation, clustering, and delineation. In brain tumor detection methods, images with tumor tissue are distinguished from images with normal tissue. In delineation methods, tumor location is determined and various tumor tissues are separated within MRI images. Classification methods are used to classify or determine whether a tumor is benign or malignant [7]. Brain tumor diagnosis using novel and automated segmentation and classification methods that are directly derived from MRI images has many advantages for clinical applications [8]. Among the advantages that motivate the use of this method, which has been discussed by many researchers, are savings in the cost of medical diagnostics, reduction of diagnosis time, and prevention of disease progression in the early stages, along with increased patient satisfaction with the use of non-invasive diagnostic methods instead of invasive methods [9,10].

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One of these new methods is the deep learning method, which is a subset of machine learning in the field of artificial intelligence and imitates the function of the human brain in processing data and patterns to solve complex decision-making problems. Deep learning is a very practical method that has provided significant advances and has found new applications in the field of health, especially in the analysis and analysis of medical images [11, 12]. Among the, deep learning models, especially CNNs have been widely used in medical images for the detection of organs and the diagnosis of diseases due to functional impairment [12,13]. By systematically reviewing recent advancements of CNNs-based techniques for brain tumor detection and classification, the primary objectives of this paper are to:

- a) provide an overview of recent deep CNN-based techniques used for brain tumor detection and classification in MRI images.
- b) identify and compare the model architectures, techniques, datasets, and performance utilized in studies from 2020 to 2025.

- c) critically analyze the limitations, and challenges associated with current CNNs models for brain tumor detection and classification and suggest potential directions for future research to enhance the clinical applicability of these models.

The comprehensive structure of the paper presented in Figure 1. After introducing brain tumors, MRI images, CNNs and the objectives of this study in Section 1, the background Section 2 provides fundamental concepts of brain tumor, MRI images and CNNs in detail. Section 3 introduces materials and methods used to search and select articles related to the focus of the review. Section 4 highlights the standard CNN-based existing techniques, datasets, preprocessing techniques and performance evaluation metrics which are used for brain tumor detection and classification tasks as found in the reviewed articles. The performance analysis and challenges of covered studies present in section 5. The summary of this paper and some future directions in this field of study are presented in Section 6.

Figure 1. Outline of the Systematic Review Paper

2. Background

In this section we will explain about brain tumor and its types, MRI images and their types, followed by the fundamentals of CNNs and relevant models' architecture.

2.1. Brain Tumor

The brain is an important part of the human body responsible for control and decision making. It controls the central nervous system and must be protected from injury and disease. Brain tumor is

abnormal growth of cells which increase the pressure inside the skull and damage the brain. A human brain with tumor growth shown in Figure 2 [14]. The pressure inside the skull may rise the tumor enlarge and brain damage and death are possible outcomes of this. Brain tumors can be broadly classified as malignant (cancerous) or benign (not cancerous). Brain and central nervous system tumors come in about 130 different varieties, all of which can range from benign to malignant, extremely rare to fairly common.

Figure 2. Human Brain with Tumor Growth

Source:

(<https://my.clevelandclinic.org/health/diseases/6149-brain-cancer-brain-tumor>)

Brain tumors can also be broadly categorized as primary or secondary [15]. A primary brain tumor originates in the brain and develops from the brain cells, nerve cells, or glands. There are three types of tumors in primary brain tumor: meningioma, gliomas and pituitary. Meningioma tumors originate on the membranes lining of skull and spinal canal, they are not considered brain tumors in the strict sense of the word. However, their growth may have an adverse effect on the brain, leading to a variety of problems

like memory loss, hearing and visual impairment, or even convulsions. Meningioma cases rise with age, and because the tumors grow slowly, symptoms may appear gradually over time. Since meningiomas are typically benign, medical professionals may decide to ignore asymptomatic instances. But if the tumor begins to negatively impact quality of life, doctors will either remove it surgically apply radiation therapy to treat [16]. The most typical early symptom of meningioma is a persistent headache. Tumors which arise from glial cells are known as gliomas. These cells typically maintain the integrity of the central nervous system, nourish it, remove waste from cells, and break down dead neurons.

Gliomas tumors can arise from a variety of glial cell types such as astrocytic tumors (which start in the cerebrum), oligodendroglia tumors (which are frequently seen in the frontal temporal lobes) and the most aggressive sort of glioblastomas, which start in the supporting brain tissue [17]. An aberrant growth of tumor in the pituitary gland called a pituitary tumor. The pituitary gland is a small gland in the brain which situated behind the back of nose. This gland produces hormones that have an impact on numerous other glands and other processes. The majority of pituitary tumors are benign and they don't disperse throughout the body [15]. However, they may lead the pituitary to produce an excessive or insufficient number of hormones, which could result in health issues. Overproduction of hormones by pituitary tumors will stimulate the production of hormones by other glands that will result in symptoms associated with each individual hormone. Additionally, a lot of pituitary tumors will impinge on the adjacent optic nerves and this result in visual issues [17]. Three types of tumors in primary brain tumor are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Sample of brain tumor (a) Glioma (b) Meningioma (c) Pituitary.

Secondary brain tumors account for the vast majority of brain cancers. They originate in another part of the body and spread to the brain via breast cancer, kidney cancer, or skin cancer. Secondary brain tumors are always malignant. Benign tumors do not spread from one area of the body to another [14]. Brain tumors can cause a variety of symptoms, depending on the tumor's size, location, and growth rate. Some common symptoms include: seizure, headache, nausea and vomiting and papilledema. Treatment for malignant or high-grade gliomas in brain tumor seldom achieves long-term tumor control. Even after combined surgery, chemotherapy, and radiotherapy, patients with high-grade cancerous brain glioma, such as glioblastoma, return roughly between 6 to 12 months, while patients with anaplastic astrocytoma return between 18 to 36 months [17].

2.2. Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI)

MRI is commonly used in neuroradiology and musculoskeletal radiology. During the formation of an MRI image, the patient is positioned within a strong and uniform magnetic field. This magnetic field aligns the nuclei of hydrogen atoms inside the

patient in the direction of the field. An external radio frequency (RF) pulse causes the nuclei to deviate from this orientation. Once the RF pulse is stopped, the hydrogen nuclei return to their initial alignment in the externally imposed magnetic field, while emitting RF signals as they lose energy, as illustrated in Figure 4.

Hydrogen atoms have the natural state of rotation axis that has no fixed orientation as they rotate with spinning system. They further have an ability to settle in an ordered manner in the presence of a magnetic field. An RF pulse, is first employed to disrupt the magnetization of the hydrogen atoms in relation to the magnetic field. After the RF pulse the atoms got relaxed back to original position and in this process, they emit signal and this signal is used to generate an image [18,19]. The strength of the field impacts the frequency of the emitted RF signals from the hydrogen nucleus as it resumes in its original position. A specialized computer system able to determine where the localized RF signal coming from each individual hydrogen nucleus, and determines the intensity and other parameters of every RF signal on the basis of the above-stated aspects.

Figure 4. Magnetic Resonance Imaging Hydrogen Nuclei [19]

The term 'gray scale' is used to depict the signals and assigns them a value ranging from white to black on the detector. A major difference of MRI with digital X-Ray scope is that MRI images are created depending on the nature of the tissues make-up and hence capable of showing different type of pathologies when compared to MRI absorptions of X-Ray [20]. This property makes MRI very relevant especially in the diagnosis of the following conditions in the spine like herniated discs, ligament tears and soft tissue tumors. MRI proves even more capable than CT scan in establishing differences in soft tissues

in particular. Two fundamental sequences in MRI are called: T1-weighted and T2-weighted sequences. The "weighting" aspect is the use of the properties of hydrogen atoms facing the magnetic field exposure. T1-weighted images normally present water as signal loss (dark) with fat as signal gain (bright) while other body tissues create an interface in between. However, on T2-weighted images, water is represented as bright and fat as dark (and tissues are in between). There are several other extended sequences or variants of the above basic sequences including gradient echo and fluid attenuated inversion recovery (FLAIR) [6,20]. The

sample T1-weighted, T2-weighted, and FLAIR weighted sequences are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Various MRI Sequences (a) T1-weighted, (b) T2-weighted and (c) FLAIR image

2.3. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)

CNNs are a type of deep neural networks used for analysis of the structured grid data, such as images. It built up from a series of layers with particular operations. In general, the input layer represents pixel

values of the images entering the networks followed by multiple convolution layers that employ filters to recognize specific pattern and features of images. ReLu is one of the mechanisms to bring non-linearity in the

Figure 6. CNN Architecture

model. Pooling layers reduce the size of the convolved features in order to make more efficient subsequent computations. Flattening is used to reshape the output into a vector of a given fixed size. The fully connected layers utilize high-level feature maps to help in decision making [13, 19, 22]. A generalized CNN architecture is shown in Figure 6.

2.3.1. Layers of CNNs

A typical CNN architecture consists of seven layer. Following is the brief description of each layer.

a) **Input Layer:** This is the first layer, where the raw input data is fed into the network. In the case of

image processing, this is the pixel values of the input image [21].

b) **Convolutional layer:** The convolutional layer is a fundamental operation in CNNs, and plays a crucial role in extracting features from input data, particularly in grid-like structures such as images. The convolutional operation involves a kernel, also known as the filter, sliding over the input data and computing the dot product at each position. Kernel is a small metrics of size $(2n + 1) \times (2n + 1)$, that is used to extract the features from the image. The values in the kernel represent the weights that the convolutional operation will learn during the training process [20, 21, 22, 23]. There

are multiple convolutional layers in a CNNs, each with varying number and sizes of kernel.

- c) **Activation Function:** Activation functions are essential components of CNNs that introduce nonlinearity, enabling the network to learn complex patterns. Common activation functions include: ReLU, sigmoid, and softmax. ReLU is an activation function which is applied element wise to present non-linearity in the model. When it receives negative input it returns 0, however for any positive value x it returns that value back [21, 22, 25, 27]. Sigmoid activation function is used in binary classification of input layer and provides the output value between 1 and 0. It can be calculated by using the following formula [22, 23].

$$s(x) = \frac{1}{1+e^{-x}} \quad (1)$$

SoftMax activation function is a subset of sigmoid activation function which is used in multi-classification. It can be calculated by using the following formula [22, 23].

$$s(x_i) = \frac{e^{x_i}}{\sum_{j=1}^n e^{x_j}} \quad (2)$$

where, x_i is the specific element calculating the probability for while x_j represent each element in the vector participating in the summation of all elements.

- d) **Pooling Layer:** Pooling layers are designed to reduce the data dimensionality by merging multiple neuron's output from a layer to another single neuron in the subsequent layer. Pooling can be performed local or global. Local pooling combines small cluster like 2×2 whereas global pooling processes the entire set of neurons in a convolutional layer. Pooling operations can determine either the maximum or an average value. Maximum pooling selects the greatest value within a neuron cluster from the previous layer, and average pooling computes the mean value of outputs from a cluster of neurons from the same layer [20, 22, 23].
- e) **Flattening:** The flattening layer converts the output from the pooling layers into a one-dimensional vector, preparing it for input layer of fully connected [23].

- f) **Fully Connected (Dense) Layers:** Dense layer is the traditional neural network layer where each neuron is connected to every neuron in the previous and subsequent layers. These layers integrate high level features and make decisions based on the learned representations [20, 22, 23].
- g) **Output Layer:** The output layer is the final layer in network where desired predications are obtained [20].

2.3.2. Deep CNN Architectures

Following are various types of convolutional neural networks commonly used to perform detection and classification. A quick comparative overview of these architecture is presented Table 1.

- a) **LeNet:** The LeNet is a simple CNN known for its shallow architecture with only five main layers. The performance of LeNet-5 depends on factors such as the choice of optimizer and learning rate. Selecting the right combination of these parameters can significantly improve accuracy. The architecture consists of 2 convolutional layers that extract spatial features, 2 pooling layers that reduce dimensionality while retaining key information, and 2 fully connected layers that handle classification. LeNet-5 remains an important reference model in deep learning, especially for understanding the fundamental concepts of CNN design and training. [22, 31].
- b) **AlexNet:** The AlexNet introduced several innovations such as, the use of ReLU activations, dropout regularization, and GPU-based training, that transformed the field of computer vision. The architecture consists of 8 layers of which 5 convolutional layers that extract visual features and 3 fully connected layers that perform classification. Max-pooling layers are placed between convolutional layers to reduce dimensionality while preserving key spatial information. The network processes input images of size $227 \times 227 \times 3$, allowing it to capture complex visual patterns and hierarchical representations. AlexNet's success demonstrated the power of deep CNNs and paved the way for modern architectures like VGG, ResNet, and Inception [19, 32].

- c) VGGNet: The Visual Geometry Group Network (VGGNet) is a convolutional neural network architecture to enhance deep learning model performance. It uses small 3×3 convolutional filters stacked deep within the network. The most common variants are VGG16 and VGG19, containing 16 and 19 weight layers, respectively. The VGG16 model includes 13 convolutional layers, five max-pooling layers, and three fully connected layers, processing input images of size $224 \times 224 \times 3$. Each convolution uses stride 1 and padding to maintain spatial resolution, while max-pooling layers with 2×2 filters reduce dimensionality. The fully connected layers at the end, typically with 4096, 4096, and 1000 neurons, are each followed by a ReLU activation function to introduce nonlinearity. The simplicity and depth of VGGNet made it a key foundation for more advanced architectures such as ResNet and DenseNet. [28, 29].
- d) GoogLeNet: The GoogLeNet is a deeper CNN model of its time. Its key innovation is the introduction of the Inception module, a unique architectural component designed to improve both computational efficiency and accuracy. GoogLeNet consists of eight inception modules along with two standard convolutional layers, two pooling layers, and one fully connected layer. Each inception module includes multiple parallel convolutional operations, generally 6 convolutional layers and 1 pooling layer that capture features at different scales before combining them into a single output. In total, the network contains 56 convolutional layers. The standard input image size for GoogLeNet is 256×256 pixels, allowing it to process high-resolution images effectively while maintaining efficiency through its optimized architecture. [16, 30].
- e) R-CNN: Region-based Convolutional Neural Network (R-CNN) is a deep learning model for object detection in image processing. It classifies image regions and generates bounding boxes around detected objects. The architecture combines two main components: a region proposal module that identifies potential regions of interest (RoIs) and a detection module that classifies these regions. Initially, the model extracts region proposals from the input image using selective search. Each proposed region is then passed through a standard CNN to extract feature representations. These features are fed into fully connected layers that determine the presence or absence of specific objects and refine the bounding box coordinates around them. Although accurate, R-CNN is computationally expensive because it processes each region independently [24, 25].
- f) Fast R-CNN: Fast Region-based Convolutional Neural Network (Fast R-CNN) is an advanced object detection framework that improves both the speed and accuracy of R-CNN. It integrates convolutional neural network (CNN) features with a Region Proposal Network (RPN) to efficiently identify and classify objects within an image. The architecture begins with standard convolutional and pooling layers to extract deep feature maps from the entire image. These feature maps are then processed through a Region of Interest (RoI) pooling layer, which converts region proposals into fixed-size feature vectors. These vectors pass through fully connected layers for classification and bounding box regression, enabling precise localization and categorization of multiple objects. By sharing convolutional computations across regions and integrating proposal generation within the same network, Fast R-CNN achieves significant improvements in detection speed and computational efficiency compared to the original R-CNN [26, 27].
- g) ResNet: Residual Network (ResNet) is a CNN architecture designed to address the degradation problem that occurs in deep neural networks when additional layers fail to improve the performance. The core idea of ResNet is the use of residual connections or skip connections, which allow the output of one layer to bypass intermediate layers and be added directly to a later layer. This structure enables the model to learn residual mappings instead of direct mappings, making training of deep networks more stable and efficient. ResNet leverages transfer learning to achieve superior classification accuracy across various applications. The architecture can contain

hundreds or even thousands of layers, with popular variants including ResNet-18, ResNet-34, ResNet-50, ResNet-101, and ResNet-152. The standard input image size for ResNet is $224 \times 224 \times 3$, consistent with ImageNet preprocessing standards [28, 29].

- h) MobileNet: MobileNet is a lightweight CNN architecture designed to deliver high performance on devices with limited computing power. It achieves efficiency by decomposing standard convolutions into two simpler operations: depth wise convolution, which applies a single filter per input channel, and pointwise convolution, which uses 1×1 convolutions to combine the outputs of the depthwise layer. This separation drastically reduces computational cost while maintaining accuracy. MobileNet also incorporates batch normalization and ReLU activations after each convolution to stabilize training and improve feature learning. Depending on the version, the

model typically accepts input image sizes such as 130×224 or 140×224 pixels. Its design makes it ideal for mobile and embedded vision applications where speed and resource efficiency are critical [32,33].

DenseNet, CNN architecture built around the concept of dense connectivity between layers. In DenseNet, each layer receives inputs from all preceding layers and passes its own feature maps to all subsequent layers. This design ensures maximum information flow throughout the network, allowing later layers to reuse previously learned features rather than relearning them. As a result, DenseNet improves gradient propagation, reduces redundancy, and often requires fewer parameters compared to traditional CNNs. Every layer in the model contributes to the collective feature representation, making the architecture highly efficient in both training and feature reuse [34, 35].

Table 1. A comparative overview of the various CNN architectures

Model	Year/ Developer(s)	Key Concept	Architecture	Input Size	Applications
LeNet-5	1998 Yann LeCun et al. (AT&T Bell Labs)	Shallow CNN	7 layers (2 conv, 2 pooling, 2 FC, 1 output)	$32 \times 32 \times 1$	Handwritten digit recognition
AlexNet	2012 Alex Krizhevsky, Ilya Sutskever, Geoffrey Hinton (University of Toronto)	Deep CNN ReLU, dropout, & GPU training;	8 layers (5 conv + 3 FC)	$227 \times 227 \times 3$	Image classification (ImageNet)
VGGNet (VGG16 / VGG19)	2014 Karen Simonyan & Andrew Zisserman (University of Oxford, VGG Group)	Deep CNN with uniform 3×3 filters	VGG16: 16 layers (13 conv + 3 FC) / VGG19: 19 layers (16 conv + 3 FC)	$224 \times 224 \times 3$	Image classification, feature extraction
GoogLeNet (Inception v1)	2014 Christian Szegedy et al. (Google)	Inception modules for multi-scale feature extraction with fewer parameters	22 layers deep; 9 inception modules + FC layers	$256 \times 256 \times 3$	Image classification
R-CNN	2014 Ross Girshick et al. (University of California, Berkeley)	Region-based CNN	Uses selective search \rightarrow CNN \rightarrow fully connected layers	$224 \times 224 \times 3$ (varies)	Object detection

Model	Year/ Developer(s)	Key Concept	Architecture	Input Size	Applications
Fast R-CNN	2015 Ross Girshick (Microsoft Research)	Improved Region-based CNN	CNN backbone + RoI pooling + 2 FC layers	Variable	Object detection
ResNet	2015 Kaiming He et al. (Microsoft Research)	Introduces skip (residual) connections to solve degradation in deep networks	50–152 layers with residual (skip) connections	224×224×3	Classification, detection, recognition
MobileNet	2017 Andrew G. Howard et al. (Google)	Lightweight CNN, uses efficient depthwise separable convolutions	28 layers (depthwise + pointwise convs)	224×224×3 (varies)	Mobile and embedded vision
DenseNet	2017 Gao Huang et al. (Cornell / Tsinghua / Facebook AI Research)	Densely connected as each layer connects to all others for feature reuse	121–201 layers (dense blocks + transition layers)	224×224×3	Classification, segmentation, medical imaging

3. Materials and Methods

To perform detailed and systematic review of the contemporary approaches in brain tumor detection and classification with deep CNNs at first, we conducted structured search on the most cited academic databases including PubMed, ScienceDirect, Springer, and IEEE Access. The search was limited to the studies published between

2020-2025 with emphasis on MRI based brain tumor detection and classification using deep CNNs. In this concern keywords like brain tumor detection, brain tumor classification, deep CNNs, convolutional neural network (CNN) was used employing Boolean operators (OR, AND) and filters. Table 2 presents the number of articles which were found and selected from various databases for this study.

Table 2. Number of articles found and selected for this study

<i>Databases</i>	<i>Found</i>	<i>Selected</i>
<i>PubMed</i>	100	15
<i>IEEE Access</i>	10	5
<i>ScienceDirect</i>	50	10
<i>Google Scholar</i>	150	20
<i>Total</i>	310	50

Article Selection Criteria

The following two criteria were used to include and excluded studies for final review:

- Inclusion Criteria: The studies were included if they (a) applied deep CNNs techniques and talk

about detection or classification of brain tumors, and (b) reported relevant performance metrics, including accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, and F1-score, and (c) have used brain MRI images and (d) published in peer-reviewed journal proceedings between the years 2020 and 2025.

- b) Exclusion Criteria: The studies were excluded if they (a) did not apply CNNs techniques and did not perform detection or classification of brain tumors, or (b) were concentrated on methods other than deep CNN, or (c) have not used brain MRI images or (d) did not report relevant performance metrics, or (e) not published in peer-reviewed journal proceedings between the years 2020 and 2025.

Using the above criteria, 310 studies were identified out of which 50 studies were selected for this study that met inclusion criteria after screening titles, abstracts and full texts. The flow of searching and selection of articles for this study is illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Search and Selection Method for the Research Papers

4. Literature Review

We perform a literature review of 50 research papers to evaluate the effectiveness of deep CNNs for brain CNNs algorithms for detection and classification of brain tumor in the past six years. Figure 8 depicts the year wise number of the research articles reviewed.

This section presents the detailed overview of the studies published between 2020-2025 on brain tumor detection and classification using deep CNN-based techniques in MRI images. Section 4.1 presents the standard methodology for brain tumor detection and classification using CNNs -based techniques in MRI images followed by Section 4.2 that presents the

tumor detection and classification through MRI scans. There has been more use of deep

broader classification of various CNN-based techniques found in the reviewed articles. Section

4.3 introduces the popular available datasets which have been used in the research articles reviewed in the form of a table. Section 4.4 outlines the preprocessing techniques used in the reviewed papers, Finally, Section 4.5 presents a brief overview of the performance evaluation which are used in reviewed studies for model performance evaluating.

Figure 8. Year wise Statistics of Research Papers Reviewed

4.1. Standard Methodology of CNN-based Techniques

The deep CNN-based techniques for brain tumor detection and classification frame are described in Figure 9. It consists of four steps.

Figure 9. The workflow of CNN-based brain tumor classification study

Step 1. Input image 2D or 3D brain MRI samples are fed into the model for classification

task.

Step 2. Preprocess the images which require various operations such as skull removal to eliminate non-brain tissues, bias field correction compensates for scanner-related intensity variations, intensity normalization to ensure consistent brightness and contrast across all MRI scans, and image registration aligns multimodal or time-series data within a common spatial framework. Resizing standardizes image dimensions for CNN input, while noise reduction and histogram equalization improve image clarity and contrast to highlight tumor features. Data

augmentation is done to increase dataset diversity through transformations such as rotation, flipping, and scaling to improve model robustness and generalization.

Step 3. The pre-processed dataset is propagated into the CNN model for training and testing processes.

Step 4. After training and testing of the CNN model by dataset, in the final step classification performance of the CNN model is evaluated using quantitative performance metrics such as accuracy, precision,

sensitivity(recall), specificity, F1 score and area under the curve, and other relevant metrics.

4.2. Existing CNN-based Techniques for Brain Tumor Classification

CNNs are the backbone of deep learning for brain tumor detection and classification with high performance and feature extraction abilities and extracted complex features automatically from MRI images. Various studies conducted between 2020 and 2025 suggest that deep CNN-based techniques developed over the past six years can be broadly classified into four main categories as follows:

- a) Custom CNN Models: These CNN-based architectures are often designed from scratch, typically less complex than deep CNN models and feature a few convolutional blocks to prevent overfitting using small dataset [14,15,36,37].
- b) Deep CNN Models: These types of CNN-based techniques using established deep architectures which helped defined modern computer vision models such as VGGNet, ResNet, DenseNet which may have more than hundreds of layers. Their depth allows them to learn a rich hierarchy of features, from simple edges to complex tumor structures [39,45,51].
- c) Pretrained CNN Models (Transfer Learning): These kinds of CNN models have trained on one task and reuse and modify the models for

another tasks. Researchers instead of training a deep model which build from scratch, start with a model which pre-trained on the huge amount of data like ImageNet to avoid time-consuming and require less computational power to train the model [32,38,40,41,43].

- d) Hybrid CNN Models: These models combine the combine the CNNs with other models, techniques or multiple CNN to improve the performance of the models. The common hybrid models include CNN+ machine learning classifiers like SVM, KNN, in which CNNs used as a feature extractors and machine learning models like SVM or KNN used for classification task [46,53,60,63,66].

4.3. Dataset

Deep Learning-based models require a large amount of data for training and testing of the classification tasks. In this regard, sufficient number of datasets are made available for research purpose. [Table 3](#) briefly lists the names of some of the datasets. All of these datasets have been used by the research work reviewed in this paper but Kaggle datasets have been used more popularly due to its large size and better visualization properties. The format column introduces the format of images which include the datasets. The description column has brief information about datasets. At least, source column points the web addressing where dataset is available that researchers have used.

Table 3. List of selected dataset

Dataset / Source	Format	Description
Kaggle [81]	JPG file	A data science competition platform and online community of data scientists and machine learning practitioners under Google LLC
Figshare [82]	.mat file	A digital repository platform designed for the open sharing of scholarly outputs. Figshare provides a secure and accessible space for hosting diverse research materials, including datasets, figures, and supplementary files
BRATS [83]	.dcm file	The BRATS datasets are considered to be the most difficult MRI datasets issued at different times throughout the years.
Harvard [84]	mpg file	A website that provides dozens of real brain images, both normal and diseased

Private [85]	JPG	The private datasets are not freely accessible; they are collecting clinically relevant research for brain tumor classification and detection task.

4.4. Pre- processing Techniques

Images often suffer from noise degradation which can occur during capture, transmission and other stages. Removing noise is essential in image processing because it significantly impact on the quality of the images. Image preprocessing involves several steps to enhance raw image data for further analysis. These steps include noise reduction, contrast enhancement, smoothing, sharpening, image restoration, histogram equalization, normalization, image data augmentation and others. The preprocessing techniques which are used by most of the researchers in reviewed studies include:

- a) **Contrast Enhancement:** MRI images typically have low contrast, making them less visually distinct. To improve their visibility, image enhancement can be applied at either the hardware or software level. Contrast enhancement is a technique used to enhance the visual quality of an image, making it more suitable for specific applications. By improving image clarity, this process facilitates easier and faster analysis while also revealing hidden features. One of the most widely used methods for enhancing MRI images is histogram equalization [15,53].
- b) **Resizing:** A requirement for deep neural networks is that input images must be of a uniform, predetermined size. Consequently, any images that are too large must be resized prior to processing. This is typically accomplished by either cropping background areas or by reducing the image dimensions through interpolation [37,40,41].
- c) **Skull Stripping:** Skull stripping is a preprocessing technique in medical image analysis, specifically for magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) of the brain. It involves removing non-brain regions such as the skull, scalp, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF), leaving only the brain tissue [15,65].
- d) **Intensity Normalization:** Normalization is a critical preprocessing step for CNN models applied to medical imaging. Since MR image intensities are not standardized and vary with scanner type and acquisition parameters, models trained on non-normalized data are ill-conditioned. To mitigate scanner-induced heterogeneity, techniques like min-max normalization (rescaling pixel values to a fixed interval) and z-score normalization (standardizing the data to a mean of zero and unit variance) are employed to standardize the input data [32,37,39].
- e) **Data Augmentation:** To ensure effective generalization, CNNs necessitate substantial training data, with a standard heuristic suggesting a dataset ten times larger than the number of model parameters to prevent overfitting [38]. Data augmentation addresses the challenge of limited data, a common issue in specialized fields like brain tumor classification. This approach mitigates data scarcity and class imbalance by generating new training samples through geometrical transformations including rotation, reflection (flipping), scaling, translation, and cropping on the original images [14, 36, 37, 41].
- f) **Noise Reduction:** Image denoising removes noise from the image. It is also known as 'Image Smoothing'. The image is convolved with a low pass filter kernel which gets rid of high-frequency content like edges of an image [65,66,76].
- g) **Bias Field Correction:** Compensates for scanner-related intensity variations to achieve uniform contrast.
- h) **Registration (Alignment):** Aligns images from different MRI modalities (e.g., T1, T2, FLAIR) or time points into a common spatial framework.

- i) Segmentation Mask Generation: Isolates and labels tumor regions for accurate supervised learning and evaluation.

4.5. Performance Evaluation Metrics

In detecting and classifying problem, performance evaluation shows the ability of model performance which classify or identify objects in images. Evaluation is important for determining the test accuracy of the CNN and it can generalize from the

given training dataset to unseen data, as well as to comparatively analyze CNN's performance to other models. confusion matrix is the tabular form that compares actual data with predicted data and show true positive (TP), true negative (TN), false positive (FP) and false negative (FN) and it helps in understanding the model better and for what classes the model makes errors [2, 19, 38]. Table 4 presents the confusion matrix while the commonly used metrics based on confusion matrix are shown in Table 5.

Table 4. Confusion Matrix

Predicted \ Actual	Positive (Tumor Present)	Negative (No Tumor)
	True Positive (TP) correctly predicted tumor cases	False Negative (FN) tumor cases incorrectly predicted as no tumor
Positive (Tumor Present)	True Positive (TP) correctly predicted tumor cases	False Negative (FN) tumor cases incorrectly predicted as no tumor
Negative (No Tumor)	False Positive (FP) non-tumor cases incorrectly predicted as tumor	True Negative (TN) correctly predicted non-tumor cases

Table 5. Summary of the commonly used metrics

Metrics	Description	Mathematical Representation	Reference
Accuracy	Accuracy is a metrics which use for evaluating the performance of classification models and it measures the number of correctly classified instances to total number of instances.	$\frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$	[46,47,48]
Precision	Precision is associated with random errors and used to express the relative quality of positive identifications in relation to true positive samples. This means that the high degree to which an algorithm got nearer to the corresponding results than getting at irrelevant.	$\frac{TP}{TP + FP}$	[44,47,48]
Metrics	Description	Mathematical Representation	Reference
Sensitivity (Recall)	Sensitivity (Recall) describes the completeness of the positive predictions relative to the ground truth. If recall is high means that model returned most of the relevant result.	$\frac{TP}{TP + FN}$	[46,47,48]
Specificity	Specificity measures the ability of the model to correctly identify negative instances (non-tumorous regions).	$\frac{TN}{TN + FP}$	[46,47,48]

F1-score	The F1-score calculates the test accuracy and is constructed as weighted average of the precision and recall	$2 \times \frac{Precision \times Recall}{Precision + Recall}$	[44,47,48]
Intersection over Union (IoU)	The performance of an object detector on a given dataset is judged by an evaluates measure known as intersection over union (IoU).	$\frac{TP}{TP + FP + FN}$	[57]
Dice Similarity Coefficient	This metric is the harmonic mean between precision and sensitivity.	$\frac{TP}{\frac{1}{2}(2TP+FP+FN)}$	[57]

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section provides an overview of the research papers focusing on brain tumor classification using CNN techniques. Section 5.1 presents the quantitative analysis of CNN-based models, all the important key elements of each reviewed article published from 2020 to 2025. Section 5.3 provides summary of the comparative analysis. Finally, Section 5.4 introduce the limitations and challenges of the selected studies which are found.

5.1 Quantitative Analysis of Studies Included

In the recent years researchers focused on CNN-based techniques for brain tumor detection and classification in MRI images. They overcome the limitations of previous deep learning and machine

datasets, preprocessing techniques, performance evaluation metrics used by the reviewed studies on brain tumor detection and classification. In Section 5.2 provides an overview and comparative analysis of the included studies of

learning based approaches for brain tumor classification task. Figure 10 shows the usage of available deep CNN-based models used in the research articles we have reviewed, published between 2020-2025, for brain tumor detection and classification, including custom CNN models, VGG, AlexNet, ResNet, GoogLeNet, DenseNet, and EfficientNet. This distribution shows that custom CNN architecture remains popular for brain tumor classification, while other models are selected based on specific needs for efficiency or advanced feature extraction

Figure 10. The models used in the articles which are reviewed

5.1.1. Dataset Utilization and Accessibility

CNNs-based models require a large amount of data for training and testing purpose. In this regard different datasets are available for

research purpose in Kaggle, Figshare and other free access platforms. Figure 11 illustrates the datasets used in the recent past six years we have reviewed for brain tumor detection and

classification using deep CNN models. The bellow pie chart indicates that most of the researchers have used Kaggle dataset due to its large size and visualization for brain tumor detection and classification tasks during the years 2020-2025.

Figure 11. The dataset used in the reviewed articles

5.1.2. Preprocessing and Image

Enhancement Techniques

Image preprocessing techniques use for improving the image quality and performance of the CNNs-based models. Figure 12 shows the usage of the most commonly used preprocessing techniques for addressing problems in brain tumor classification,

including data augmentation, normalization, resizing, skull stripping, contrast enhancement, and noise reduction during the past six years. The bar chart indicates that, since 2020-2025 data augmentation has been used in the majority of studies to ease data scarcity and overfitting problems.

Figure 12. Usage of preprocessing techniques in the reviewed articles

5.1.3. Evaluation Metrics for Model Performance

Performance evaluation metrics play a vital role in elucidating the CNNs-based models' performance. The evaluation metrics employed in the studies published between 2020-2025 on brain tumor detection and classification are represented in

figure 13. Each metric targets a different aspect of model performance. The below sunburst chart demonstrates that accuracy is still the most widely used metric, but many times it is combined with other metrics such as precision, recall, F1-score and specificity to provide a better picture of performance, especially in critical cases such as a medical diagnosis.

Figure 13. The number of metrics used in the reviewed articles

5.2. Comparative Analysis of Studies

Included

This section presents a detailed overview and a comparative analysis of studies published between 2020-2025, focusing on CNN-based techniques for brain tumor detection and classification in MRI images. Table 6 summarizes the techniques, datasets, sample size, classification type, and performance metrics of reviewed studies.

In the year 2020, Togacar et al. [36] proposed BrainMRNet, a novel CNN architecture for brain tumor detection and classification in MRI images. The authors used 235 brain MRI images (155 tumor and 98 notumor) for binary classification. They compared BrainMRNet with pretrained models like AlexNet, GoogleNet, and VGG16, but BrainMRNet achieved the highest accuracy (96.05%). Data augmentation was used to improve the size

image of dataset for achieving better accuracy. The authors in [15], introduced 2D CNN architecture to classify three types of brain tumor glioma, meningioma and pituitary MRI images which include 3064 images collected from 233 patients. In this study before training the model preprocessing techniques like skull stripping, contrast enhancement and noise reduction used for improving the quality of the images. The model achieved classification accuracy of 91.3%. A multi-class classification brain tumor MRI images has been discussed by the authors in [37]. They compared two CNN architectures, the first has one convolutional layer and the second one has two convolutional layers, and both models used data augmentation for increasing the sample size, normalization and other techniques of pre-processing to standardize the data. 253 MRI images augmented to 2065 samples and fed to models, the first model achieved (85%) higher accuracy than the other model. The authors in [14] have developed a lightweight 22-layer CNN architecture to classify three types of brain tumor including glioma, meningioma, and pituitary from 3064 MRI images which were acquired from 233 patients. In this study data augmentation techniques were used to increase dataset diversity, resulting in 9192 samples. The model's performance was evaluated by record-wise and subject-wise 10-fold cross-validation, the record-wise cross-validation on the augmented dataset achieved the highest accuracy of 96%. In another article [38], the authors have pointed out a deep CNN technique for brain tumor detection and classification in MRI images utilizing a pre-trained VGG16 architecture. The dataset was sourced from Kaggle which comprised 235 MRI images. They used different preprocessing techniques like noise reduction, thresholding, normalization to standardize the images and used data augmentation to increase the sample size of the data. The max-pooling layer was replaced by a global average pooling layer and frozen convolutional layers were used to reduce training time and overfitting. The model achieved a classification accuracy of 96%.

Next year in 2021 Gokila Brindha et al. [39], compared the performance of an artificial neural network (ANN) and a convolutional neural network (CNN) for the binary classification of brain MRI images into "normal" and "tumor" categories. The authors used a dataset of 2065 MRI images sourced from GitHub, the

authors pre-processed the data by resizing all images. In contrast, the custom CNN model which incorporated multiple convolutional, max-pooling, and dropout layers achieved the highest accuracy of 89%. Their custom ANN architecture achieved a lower test accuracy of 65.21%, which indicated overfitting. In the study [40], Sharma et al. have proposed a CNN-based technique for brain tumor classification using transfer learning with VGG16 architecture. The dataset was collected from ImageNet, BRATS which comprised 3064 MRI images. Preprocessing techniques and data augmentation were used to standardize and increase the sample size of the dataset. The model achieved an accuracy of 90%. The authors in [41] have explored different deep CNN architectures using transfer learning for brain tumor classification in MRI images. This study used 253 MRI images applying pretrained models like ResNet50, VGG16, VGG19, NASNetLarge, Xception, and DenseNet. Preprocessing techniques like cropping, resizing and augmenting were used to enhance the training effectiveness. Among all the models VGG16 and ResNet50 achieved the highest accuracy of 96%. A brain tumor classification framework proposed in [42] which combined CNNs with machine learning approaches using pretrained deep NN and ensemble techniques. This study used 3064 MRI images collected from 233 patients for classifying three types of brain tumor like glioma, meningioma, and pituitary. The authors used pre-trained Inception-v3 and Xception models for feature extraction and softmax, SVM, RF, KNN and ensemble learning for classification tasks. Inception-v3 with ensemble classifier achieved the highest accuracy of 94.34% among all models. The authors in [32] introduced a deep CNN architecture for brain tumor detection and classification in MRI images using MobileNetV2 model. In this study 2475 MRI images were used to categorize brain tumors into three types: glioma, meningioma, and pituitary, sourced from Kaggle and the model achieved 94% testing accuracy. Fine-tuning with depth-wise separable convolutions allowed the model to train faster and achieve enhanced accuracy.

In year 2022, a novel end-to-end automated brain tumor classification framework called BrainNet was proposed by the authors in [43]. In this study transfer learning using ResNet101 was employed for feature

extraction from four MRI modalities (T1, T1CE, T2) and used PCA, SVM for classification. Among the other classifier SVM achieved the highest classification accuracy of 96.7%, with reduced prediction time. The study in ^[44] proposed multi-layered CNN architecture to classify brain tumor into four classes glioma, meningioma, pituitary, and no-tumor using 3264 MRI images sourced from Kaggle. In this study normalization and resizing used to standardized the data for classification task. The proposed model achieved 96% accuracy for classification performance across the four categories. The authors in ^[45] implemented VGG16-based CNN architecture with 13 convolution layers and five pooling layers for feature extraction using 253 MRI images which collected from Kaggle for brain tumor detection and classification. In this study data augmentation techniques like flipping, rotation, and translation applied to increase the sample size of the small dataset. The proposed model achieved 96% accuracy out-performing other architectures such as ResNet-50 89% and Inception-V3 75%. In another study in ^[46] the authors proposed hybrid CNN-KNN architecture, CNN used for feature extraction and K-NN used for classification. In this study authors used 2870 MRI images collected from Kaggle with four tumor classes no tumor, glioma, meningioma, and pituitary. The preprocessing techniques like images resizing used from 256×256 to 60×60 to reduce computational complexity. The CNN-KNN model achieved an overall accuracy of 95.7%. In ^[47] the authors introduced the ResNet-50 architecture with transfer learning for brain tumor detection and classification. The model was trained and tested using 3064 MRI images containing three tumor types glioma, meningioma, and pituitary collected from Figshare dataset. In this study data augmentation techniques like rotation and flipping were used to increase dataset variability. The proposed ResNet-50 model achieved 95.3% accuracy. The authors in ^[48] have presented a comparative analysis of three common deep CNN models VGG-16, Inception-v3, and ResNet50 for brain tumor classification using MRI images. In this study preprocessing techniques such as image resizing, normalization, and augmentation over 253 brain MRI images used to increase the sample size and standardized the images for training the models. Among the three models

VGG-16 achieved the highest accuracy with 96% while ResNet50 reached 95% accuracy and Inception-v3 performed the worst with 78% accuracy. The study in ^[49] proposed two CNN models for both binary-class normal vs. abnormal and multi-class glioma, meningioma, pituitary classification tasks using two datasets Figshare (3064 images) and Harvard Medical (152 images). The authors used 23-layer CNN for large-scale data and VGG16 model combined with the 23-layer CNN for smaller datasets to mitigate overfitting. Preprocessing techniques included image conversion, resizing, normalization, and data augmentation used for standardized the images for training the models. The proposed model achieved 97.8% accuracy.

Later in year 2023, Saeedi et al. ^[50], proposed two CNN architecture using a novel 2D CNN and a convolutional auto-encoder network for brain tumor detection and classification utilized a dataset of 3264 MRI images categorized into four classes: glioma, meningioma, pituitary gland tumor, and healthy brains. By preprocessing and data augmentation the sample image size increased to 9792 images. The proposed 2D CNN architecture achieved accuracy of 93.45% and the auto-encoder model 90.93% accuracy. The authors in ^[51] have presented a comparative analysis of deep CNNs models for brain tumor detection and classification in MRI images. This study used a dataset of 3264 MRI images which categorized into four classes glioma, meningioma, pituitary, and no tumor. The preprocessing techniques like Gaussian and Laplacian filters, and further augmented using mirroring, rotation, shifting, and zooming were used to enhance training robustness. The proposed CNN architecture achieved accuracy of 93.3%, and transfer learning models such as ResNet-50 81.1%, VGG16 71.6%, and Inception V3 80%. In another paper in ^[52], proposed seven deep CNNs models including one custom CNN and six pre-trained architectures for multi-iclass brain tumor classification in MRI images.

This study used Figshare, SARTAJ, and Br35H datasets comprising 7023 MRI images categorized into four classes: glioma, meningioma, pituitary, and no tumor. Preprocessing techniques like image resizing, labeling, and augmentation like rotation, zoom, and brightness adjustments used for

standardizing of the dataset images. Among all the proposed models like InceptionV3, ResNet50, InceptionResNetV2, Xception, MobileNetV2, EfficientNetB0, and a generic CNN the InceptionV3 model achieved the highest average accuracy of 97.12%. A hybrid model combining a custom deep CNN SVM classifier in ^[53] introduced by the authors for brain tumor detection and classification in MRI images. This study used Figshare dataset containing of 2957 T1-weighted MRI images categorized into three tumor types glioma, meningioma, and pituitary. Preprocessing techniques including image resizing, noise reduction, contrast enhancement used to improve the quality of the images. Data augmentation was also performed to expand the dataset. The hybrid CNN-SVM model achieved a classification accuracy of 96.00%. In the study ^[54], the authors have proposed a modified CNN architecture integrating elements of DenseNet, VGG16, and basic CNNs for brain tumor detection and classification in MRI images. This study used 7021 brain MRI images which containing four classes like glioma, meningioma, pituitary, and healthy. The authors compared multiple architectures including custom CNN, VGG16, DenseNet, and their own modified CNN evaluated using both standard train-test splits and 10-fold cross-validation. The modified CNN architecture achieved higher accuracy of 95% among the other models.

Al-Khuzai and Al-Jawher ^[59] in year 2024 proposed a novel 2D-to-3D fusion model for brain tumor detection and classification using a modified 3D-CNN that integrates 2D MRI images into 3D volumetric representations. In this study the model trained on the combined dataset from six Kaggle sources, creating a unified brain tumor data collection containing 16441 images, categorized into normal and abnormal cases. The proposed model achieved a classification accuracy of 88%. The authors of another publication in ^[60] have proposed comprehensive deep CNN framework for brain tumor detection and classification, combining CNNs with traditional machine learning methods like SVM. This study used BRATS dataset which contains 100 MRI images. Preprocessing techniques like normalization, skull stripping, and anisotropic diffusion to improve image quality and reduce noise. The proposed CNN-SVM model achieved an accuracy of 92.3%. In this Study ^[61], the authors compared the performance of three

deep learning models like CNN, PNN, and RNN. This study employed a dataset of 2000 MRI images categorized into glioma, meningioma, pituitary tumors, and non-tumor cases. Data preprocessing techniques like resizing, flipping, and rotation were used for augmentation to standardized the data and reducing overfitting. All models were tested with 25 hidden layers, and the CNN architecture comprising 10 convolutional layers, 5 max-pooling layers, 6 dropout layers 30% rate, a flatten layer, and 3 dense layers achieved the highest accuracy of 95%, outperforming PNN 94% and RNN 41%. In ^[62], the authors have introduced a novel three-phase deep CNNs techniques for brain tumor classification in MRI images combining object detection, segmentation, and classification. This study used two Kaggle datasets comprising over 12000 MRI images with four classes glioma, meningioma, pituitary, and no tumor. The segmented region classified using various deep CNNs including InceptionV3, DenseNet, Xception, VGG16, EfficientNetV2 B3, and CoCa. The CoCa classification model achieved the highest results with 97.60% accuracy among all the models. Another study in ^[63] introduced a hybrid deep CNN model combining a lightweight CNN with a SVM classifier for accurate brain tumor detection and classification in MRI images. In this study the public Kaggle dataset containing 2870 images with four categories like glioma, meningioma, pituitary tumor, and no tumor. Performance analysis show that the CNN-SVM model outperformed CNN-Softmax and other pre-trained models like VGG16, VGG19, ResNet18, GoogleNet and achieving 96.7% accuracy. Suryawanshi and Patil in ^[25], proposed a hybrid deep learning model combining CNN and SVM for multi-class brain tumor classification using MRI images. This study utilized both the Brats 2018 and Sartaj datasets, covering tumor types such as high-grade glioma (HGG), low-grade glioma (LGG), glioma, meningioma, and no tumor. The architecture explored three models: a custom CNN, pre-trained VGG19, and a hybrid CNN-SVM approach. For feature extraction, VGG19 and CNN were used for feature extraction, and SVM used for classification, which helped optimize performance and reduce overfitting. The CNN-SVM model outperformed the others, achieving an accuracy of 95.16%. In other study in ^[64], Khan and Park introduced a convolutional-block-

based deep learning architecture specifically designed for multiclass brain tumor detection using MRI scans. This study utilized three publicly available datasets from Kaggle comprising over 43000 MRI images across glioma, pituitary, and meningioma tumor types to train and validate the model. After optimal image resizing (100×100) and normalization, their proposed CNN employed multiple convolutional blocks with increasing filter sizes, batch normalization, max-pooling, and global average pooling for robust feature extraction. The model achieved average classification accuracy of 97.85%,

Recently in year 2025, Pande et al. [71] proposed CNN-based approach for automated brain tumor detection and classification in MRI scans. This study used a dataset of 3064 MRI images categorized into glioma, meningioma, pituitary, and non-tumor cases. Preprocessing steps such as resizing, normalization, and data augmentation (rotation, flipping, and noise addition) were applied to enhance robustness and address class imbalance, while dropout layers were used to reduce overfitting. The model achieved 96.8% accuracy. The authors in [72] used convolutional neural networks for brain tumor classification in MRI images. The proposed CNN model was trained on a dataset of 9147 MRI images categorized into glioma, meningioma, pituitary, and non-tumor classes. Preprocessing techniques such as image resizing, normalization, and data augmentation were applied to improve generalization and reduce overfitting. Experimental results showed that the model achieved 86.17% accuracy. In another paper in [73] introduced a CNN-based approach for automated brain tumor detection in MRI images. This study has used a dataset of 3260 MRI images divided into glioma, meningioma, pituitary, and non-tumor categories, the authors applied preprocessing techniques such as image resizing, normalization, and data augmentation to improve robustness and prevent overfitting. The proposed CNN architecture consisted of convolutional, max-pooling, dropout, and fully connected layers with softmax activation for classification. Experimental evaluation showed that the model achieved an accuracy of 97.2%. In this Study [74] proposed a hybrid CNNs-SVM for brain tumor detection and classification in MRI images. The approach CNNs used for automated feature extraction and SVM used for final classification, aiming to

improve accuracy over traditional methods. A dataset of 3000 MRI images including glioma, meningioma, pituitary, and non-tumor cases. The pre-processing techniques like resizing, normalization, and data augmentation used to enhance model generalization. The CNN-SVM model achieved 94.8% accuracy. Ticku et al. in [75] presented a novel approach for brain tumor detection and classification in MRI images using Quantum Convolutional Neural Networks (QCNNs). The proposed model was trained on over 3000 T1-weighted contrast-enhanced MRI images of glioma, meningioma, and pituitary tumors. Preprocessing techniques including normalization, resizing, and data augmentation used to enhance generalization. The QCNN architecture based on a 4-qubit quantum convolutional layer, achieved a testing accuracy of 92.13%, comparable to ResNet50, but reduced training time dramatically from 64.95 seconds per epoch to just 1.1 seconds. Gayathiri and Santhanam in [76] have proposed a deep CNN-based framework for brain tumor classification in MRI images using CNNs integrated with ResNet. In this study the dataset which consist of 3200 MRI images with four categories like glioma, meningioma, pituitary, and non-tumor. Preprocessing techniques like normalization, resizing, and data augmentation were applied to enhance training efficiency and reduce overfitting. The performance showed that the model achieved 96.4% accuracy. In this study [77], the authors have introduced a CNN-based framework for brain tumor detection and classification in MRI images for improving the diagnostic accuracy and reduce the dependence on manual analysis. The dataset used in this study included 3100 MRI images categorized into four classes like glioma, meningioma, pituitary, and non-tumor. Preprocessing techniques like normalization, resizing, and data augmentation were applied to improve the image quality and generalization. The model achieved an accuracy of 97.5%. The authors in [78] explored pre-trained VGG16 using transfer learning for brain tumor detection and classification in MRI images. In this study two publicly available datasets Kaggle and Figshare were used which contain 3264 MRI images. Preprocessing techniques like resizing, normalization, data augmentation, and handling of class imbalance through weights and oversampling. The fine-tuned VGG16 model achieved 85% accuracy. In another

study in [79], the authors presented a comparative analysis of ResNet18 and VGG16 architectures for brain tumor detection and classification in MRI images. The dataset used in this study containing 7509 MRI images with four categories like glioma, meningioma, pituitary, and normal. Preprocessing techniques like resizing, normalization, and data augmentation were applied. Experimental results revealed that ResNet18 with pretrained achieved the highest accuracy of 97.43% delivering strong classification performance across all tumor types with minimal errors. In other hand VGG16 trained from scratch achieved the worst 63.09% accuracy. In another study by Gencer in [80], the author has presented a comparative study of AlexNet and EfficientNetB0 models for brain tumor detection and classification in MRI images. In this study the Figshare brain tumor dataset used which contain 3064 T1-weighted MRI images with three classes like glioma, meningioma, and pituitary tumors. The images were preprocessed using resizing, RGB conversion, normalization, and augmentation before being fed into the models. AlexNet achieved 80.42% accuracy, while EfficientNetB0 outperformed with 97.87% accuracy.

Table 6: Comparative analysis of Literature reviews

Ref.	Year	Techniques Used	Dataset	Sample size	Classification type	Remark	Accuracy
Toğaçar et al. [36]	2020	Novel CNN, Residual Blocks and Data Augmentation	Kaggle	253 MRI images	Binary-Class	This study proposed a novel CNN model incorporating attention modules, residual blocks, and the hype-column technique to achieve high accuracy and used data augmentation for increasing the size of small dataset.	96.05%
Sarkar et al. [15]	2020	A custom 2D CNN, Adaptive contrast enhancement, and Skull stripping	Chinese hospitals (2005–2010)	3064 MRI images	Multi-class	This study demonstrated strong generalizability though 10-fold cross-validation and also with Preprocessing focused on improving SNR and removing non-brain tissues.	91.3%
Febrianto et al. [37]	2020	Two custom 2D CNN models, Data Augmentation, Resizing, Normalization	Kaggle	2065 MRI images	Binary-Class	This study Compared two CNN architectures. Found that a model with 2 convolutional layers and dropout has significantly better performance and reduce overfitting.	93%
Badža and Barjaktarović [14]	2020	Deep 22-layer CNN architecture, augmentation like rotation, flipping and rigorous 10-fold cross-validation both record-wise and subject-wise.	Chinese hospitals (2005–2010)	3064 MRI images	Multi-class	This study Focused on creating an efficient network 4.3 million parameters than complex pre-trained models and Introduced subject-wise cross-validation to test real-world generalization on unseen cases.	96.56%
Siddique et al. [38]	2020	Pre-trained VGG-16 model, data augmentation like rotation, shifting, brightness, shearing, and flipping.	Kaggle	253 MRI images	Binary-Class	This study Focused on creating an efficient system using modifications to replace the final max-pooling layer with a global average pooling to achieves perfect sensitivity 100%, it means that model correctly identified all tumor cases.	96%

Ref.	Year	Techniques Used	Dataset	Sample size	Classification type	Remark	Accuracy
Brindha et al. [39]	2021	Custom Artificial Neural Network (ANN) and Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)	GitHub	2065 MRI images	Binary-Class	This study addressed the compared performance of a CNN and ANN. The CNN was more suitable for image-based classification, ANN suffered from overfitting.	89%, 65%
Sharma et al. [40]	2021	Pre-trained VGG16, resizing, augmentation	BRATS	-	Binary-Class	This study compared scratch-trained with pre-trained of VGG16. The pre-trained model achieved high accuracy than scratch-trained.	90%
Qodri et al. [41]	2021	Pre-trained ResNet50, VGG16, VGG19, Xception, and DenseNet192, Data augmentation, Resizing	Kaggle	253 MRI images	Binary-Class	This study proposed five pre-trained model like ResNet50, VGG16, VGG19, Xception, and DenseNet192, ResNet50 and VGG16 achieved highest and demonstrated the power of transfer learning for MRI image analysis, particularly with limited datasets.	96%
Noreen et al. [42]	2021	Fine-tuned Inception-v3/Xception, SVM/RF/KNN/Ensemble	Figshare	3064 MRI images	Multi-class	This study used pre-trained Inceptionv3 and Xception for feature extraction and SVM, Random Forest, KNN and ensemble for classification. Inception-v3 with ensemble achieved the highest accuracy.	94.34%
Arfan et al. [32]	2021	Pre-trained MobileNetV2, Depth-wise Separable Convolutions, Batch Normalization.	Kaggle	2475 MRI images	Multi-class	This study highlighted the efficiency of MobileNetV2, which provides high accuracy with less computational demand compared to standard CNNs.	94%
Zahid et al. [43]	2022	Pre-trained ResNet101, particle swarm optimization or PSO, serial feature fusion, PCA, SVM.	BraTS2018	130200 MRI images	Multi-class	This study focused on feature optimization and fusion to reduce redundancy and computational time and achieved speedup 25.5x in prediction time while achieving high accuracy.	96.7%

Ref.	Year	Techniques Used	Dataset	Sample size	Classification type	Remark	Accuracy
Khan et al. [44]	2022	Custom convolutional neural network	Kaggle	3264 MRI images	Multi-class	This study proposed HDL2B-Tumor-Classifer using a custom CNN structure. It achieved competitive accuracy and a low miss rate.	92.13%
Alsaif et al. [45]	2022	ResNet-50, VGG-19 and VGG-16 Data augmentation like Flipping, Rotation, Translation	Kaggle	253 MRI images	Binary-Class	This study compared three CNNs model ResNet-50, VGG-19 and VGG-16. The VGG-16 model with augmentation outperformed achieved high efficiency.	96%
Shanjida et al. [46]	2022	Hybrid CNN - K-NN model	Kaggle	2870 MRI images	Multi-class	This study introduced a hybrid CNN-KNN model where CNN used for extracting features, and KNN used for classification to achieved high accuracy.	95.7%
Sahaai et al. [47]	2022	Pre-trained ResNet-50, Resizing, histogram equalization, binarization, and data augmentation like rotation, flipping.	Figshare	3064 MRI images	Multi-class	This study leveraged transfer learning with a pre-trained ResNet-50 model to achieve high accuracy while significantly reducing training time and computational cost compared to training from scratch.	95.3%
Srinivas et al. [48]	2022	Pre-trained CNN architectures VGG-16, Inception-v3, and ResNet-50. Resizing, Normalization, data augmentation like rotation, flipping.	Kaggle	233 MRI images	Binary-Class	This study compared three pre-trained models like VGG-16, Inception-v3, ResNet-50). VGG-16 had better performance than and achieved high accuracy. Transfer learning and data augmentation used for handling the small original dataset.	96%,
Khan et al. [49]	2022	A custom 23-layer CNN and a Fine-tuned VGG16 model, Resizing, data augmentation like shearing, zooming, rotation, flipping.	Figshare, Harvard Medical Dataset	3064 and 152 MRI images	Multi-Class,	This study proposed the custom 23-layer CNN used with large dataset while a hybrid VGG16 model is used for smaller datasets to avoid overfitting, also augmentation used for increasing the size of small dataset.	97.8%

Ref.	Year	Techniques Used	Dataset	Sample size	Classification type	Remark	Accuracy
Saeedi et al. [50]	2023	2D CNN, convolutional auto-encoder network, Data augmentation, Resizing, Normalization	Kaggle	3264 MRI images	Multi-class	This study proposed 2D CNN and convolutional auto-encoder network for multi-class classification and achieved high accuracy and compared with six traditional machine learning methods.	93.45%
Mahmud et al. [51]	2023	A custom CNN and Transfer Learning models including ResNet-50, VGG16, and Inception V3.	Kaggle	3264 MRI images	Multi-class	This study proposed custom CNN outperformed the pre-trained transfer learning models like ResNet-50, VGG16, Inception V3 and highlighted the challenge of training complex models like Inception V3 without high GPU resources.	93.30%
Guzmán et al. [52]	2023	A Generic CNN model and six pre-trained model like InceptionV3, ResNet50, InceptionResNetV2, Xception, MobileNetV2, and EfficientNetB, Resizing, Augmentation	Figshare, SARTAJ, Br35H).	7023 MRI images	Multi-class	This study evaluated the performance of seven CNN models one generic CNN and six pre-trained like ResNet50, InceptionV3, InceptionResNetV2, Xception, MobileNetV2, and EfficientNetB0 the inceptionV3 achieved the highest average accuracy.	97.12%
Biswas and Islam [53]	2023	Hybride CNN-SVM, Resizing, Noise reduction), Contrast enhancement, Data Augmentation	Figshare	2957 MRI images	Multi-class	This study proposed hybrid CNN-SVM model outperform models like AlexNet, GoogLeNet, VGG16 in both accuracy and computational efficiency. Preprocessing and augmentation significantly improved results	96%
Özkaraca et al. [54]	2023	Custom Dense CNN architecture, Dense Net, VGG16, Fold cross-validation	Figshare, SARTAJ, Br35H	7021 MRI images	Multi-class	This study proposed custom Dense CNN model which avoided transfer learning, used dense layers for image feature extraction, and achieved high accuracy but with increased processing time.	97%

Ref.	Year	Techniques Used	Dataset	Sample size	Classification type	Remark	Accuracy
Zebari et al. [35]	2023	DenseNet121, Resizing, Gaussian Filter Denoising, Normalization, Data Augmentation like Rotation, Shearing.	Kaggle	253 MRI images	Binary-Class	This study used data augmentation to handle a small original dataset, than used DenseNet121 for automated feature extraction and chieved high performance with augmented data.	94.83%
AlTahhan et al. [55]	2023	Pre-trained GoogleNet and AlexNet, Hybrid AlexNet-SVM and AlexNet-KNN Resizing,	Figshare, SARTAJ, and Br35h	2880 MRI images	Multi-class	This study proposed Pre-trained GoogleNet and AlexNet and hybrid AlexNet-SVM and AlexNet-KNN. The hybrid model AlexNet-KNN achieved the highest accuracy.	97%
Patil and Kirange [56]	2023	Ensemble Deep Learning: Fusion of a custom Shallow CNN, VGG16, K-fold Cross-Validation, Data Augmentation like Rotation and flipping.	Figshare	3064 MRI images	Multi-class	This study ensemble model (EDCNN) effectively handles class imbalance and reduces information loss by combining shallow and deep features. achieved high performance across all metrics.	97.77%
Asiri et al [57]	2023	ResNet50 (for classification), U-Net (for segmentation), transfer learning, focal Tversky loss.	TCGA-LGG and TCIA	590 MRI images	Binary-Class	This study Combined classification (ResNet50) and segmentation (U-Net) to improved accuracy. Outperforms previous methods in segmentation metrics.	94%
Santos [58]	2023	VGG-16, data augmentation like rotation, shifting, flipping.	Kaggle	50 MRI images	Binary-Class	This study demonstrated the application of a well-known CNN architecture VGG-16 for a medical imaging task. It highlights the importance of data augmentation to prevent overfitting and increase the size of original dataset.	80%
Al-Khuzai and Al-Jawher [59]	2024	A novel 2D-to-3D CNN fusion model, pre-trained 3D VGG16.	Kaggle	16441 MRI images	Binary-Class	This study proposed method which addressed the computational cost and overfitting issues of traditional 3D CNNs by converting 2D images to 3D.	88%

Ref.	Year	Techniques Used	Dataset	Sample size	Classification type	Remark	Accuracy
Smitha et al. [60]	2024	Combined SVM and Mask R-CNN outputs via thresholding and post-processing.	BRATS	100 MRI images	Binary-Class	This study proposed hybrid model combines traditional image processing (anisotropic diffusion), machine learning (SVM), and deep learning (Mask R-CNN) to improve accuracy and robustness.	92.3%
Thakkar et al. [61]	2024	CNN, PNN, and RNN	Kaggle	2000 MRI images	Multi-class	This study compared three deep learning models like CNN, PNN and RNN. The CNN model performance was better than the others, demonstrating its superiority for image-based classification tasks. The RNN model performed very poorly 41% accuracy.	95%
Abedini [62]	2024	YOLOv8 for object detection, InceptionV3, DenseNet, Xception, VGG16, EfficientNetV2 and CoCa	Kaggle	2272 MRI Images	Multi-class	This study Proposed YOLOv8 for detection and other CNNs models like InceptionV3, DenseNet, Xception, VGG16, EfficientNetV2, for classification and CoCa model achieved the best performance, shows the power of advanced models for MRI image detection and classification.	97.60%
Shanjida et al. [63]	2024	Hybrid CNN-SVM, CNN-Softmax , Pre-trained models like GoogleNet, VGG16, VGG19, ResNet18. Data augmentation, K-fold cross-validation.	Kaggle	2870 MRI Images	Multi-class	This study compared hybrid CNN-SVM with several pre-trained models like GoogleNet, VGG16, VGG19, ResNet18. Hybrid CNN-SVM model achieved higher accuracy than other CNNs models.	96.7%
Suryawanshi and Patil [25]	2024	A hybrid CNN-SVM model, Custom CNN, and the VGG19 architecture, Data augmentation, Noise Reduction.	Kaggle	2000 MRI Images	Multi-class	This study introduced the hybrid CNN-SVM model and compared it with both custom CNN and VGG19 models. The proposed hybrid CNN-SVM achieved high accuracy.	95.16%

Ref.	Year	Techniques Used	Dataset	Sample size	Classification type	Remark	Accuracy
Khan and Park [64]	2024	A custom Convolutional Block-Based CNN architecture, Resizing, Data augmentation	Kaggle	43475 MRI images	Multi-class	This study proposed convolutional block-based CNN model demonstrates state-of-the-art performance in multiclass brain tumor using MRI images, offering a robust, efficient, and clinically applicable solution for automated brain tumor detection and classification	97.85
Khan et al. [65]	2024	CNNs, LSTM networks, Gaussian filtering, sharpening, skull stripping), Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM)	Bahawal Victoria Hospital (Pakistan)	400 MRI images	Binary-Class	This study used traditional texture features (GLCM) with optimized feature selection; compares CNN and LSTM; preprocessing includes denoising and skull stripping used for improving the quality of images at least lower accuracy compared to modern CNN Methods.	84.50%
Peddinti et al. [66]	2024	A hybrid R-CNN, Chicken Swarm Optimization (CSO), Adaptive Fuzzy Filtering, ResNet	BRATS 2015	874 MRI images	Multi-class	This study proposed RCNN-CSO method significantly outperforms existing models (CNN, KSVM, SVM, RF) across all metrics. It uses bio-inspired optimization (CSO) for efficient feature selection to achieve high accuracy.	96%
Sarada et al. [67]	2024	ResNet50V2 architecture with added Batch Normalization, Max Pooling, and Dropout layers.	Figshare, SARTAJ, Br35H	7023 MRI Images	Multi-class	This study introduced modifications (Batch Normalization, Max Pooling, Dropout) on ResNet50V2 which improved training stability, reduced overfitting, and enhanced generalization.	96.34%
Tolba and Talal [68]	2024	Hybrid ResNet50, MobileNet, AlexNet. and Neutrosophic Sets (NS) for domain conversion	Kaggle	3263 MRI Images	Multi-class	This study introduced a novel hybrid approach by combining Neutrosophic theory with CNNs models to improve performance on a limited dataset.	75.6%
Khan et al. [69]	2024	Pre-trained DenseNet169, Random Forest (RF), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Data Augmentation like	Figshare	3064 MRI images	Multi-class	This study combined deep learning feature extraction approach like DenseNet169 with traditional ML classifiers RF, and SVM for brain tumor	95.10%

Ref.	Year	Techniques Used	Dataset	Sample size	Classification type	Remark	Accuracy
		rotation, flipping, resizing				detection and classification and achieved high accuracy.	
Chauhan et al. [70]	2024	Patch-Based Vision Transformer (PBViT), patch tokenization, DenseNet-inspired dense blocks, custom CNN, hybrid architecture combining ViT and CNN	FigShare	2327 MRI images	Multi-class	This study Introduced a novel hybrid Vision Transformer architecture used patch-based processing to capture both local and global features and integrated DenseNet and CNN layers for enhanced feature extraction and achieved high accuracy.	95.8%
Pande et al. [71]	2025	Custom convolutional neural network, Data augmentation like rotation, flipping.	Kaggle	3064 MRI images	Multi-class	This study evaluated traditional, manual feature-based methods to demonstrating CNNs' superiority in automatically learning features for brain tumor detection and classification	96.8 %
Moreno et al. [72]	2025	Pre-trained models like VGG16, DenseNet121, Inception and ResNet-v2	Kaggle	9,147 MRI images	Multi-class	This study combined an ensemble model with advanced explainability techniques to achieve both high accuracy and clinical interpretability.	86.17%
Khan et al. [73]	2025	Multi-path convolutional architecture blocks. Data augmentation	Kaggle	6380 MRI images	Multi-class	This study optimized custom architecture that achieved state-of-the-art accuracy and a fast inference time of 5.13 ms per scan.	97.52%
Semwal et al. [74]	2025	CNN – SVM, Normalization Data augmentation like rotation, shifts, zoom, and flipping.	Kaggle	3264 MRI Images	Multi-class	This study outperformed traditional ML and CNN model to achieve high precision 0.9, low recall 0.30 due to intensity clinically promising.	84.77%
Ticku et al. [75]	2025	Quantum convolutional neural network	Figshare	3064 MRI Images	Multi-class	This study achieved similar accuracy to ResNet50 but with drastically reduced training time (1.1s vs. 64.95s per epoch); shows promise for quantum efficiency in medical imaging but faces hardware and interpretability challenge.	92.13%

Ref.	Year	Techniques Used	Dataset	Sample size	Classification type	Remark	Accuracy
Gayathiri and Santhanam [76]	2025	Convolutional stacked autoencoder network or C-SAN, NLM filter, V-Net	Figshare	3064 MRI images	Multi-class	This study combined traditional feature method with deep learning, robust performance across two datasets, high sensitivity and specificity, complex multi-stage pipeline.	92%
Chhotray et al. [77]	2025	Pre-trained models like VGG16, ResNet50, and DenseNet121, cascaded Custom-CNN architecture.	Figshare	3064 MRI images	Multi-class	This study combined pre-trained models in cascaded custom CNN antichatter and shows strong generalization across datasets.	97.34%
Muntahaa and Tauheed [78]	2025	Pre-trained VGG16 model, Data augmentation like rotation, flipping, zoom, Grad-CAM	Kaggle and Figshare	3264 MRI images	Multi-class	This study focused on real-world generalizability by merging datasets to create variability and its use Grad-CAM to build trust and transparency in the model's predictions for clinical use.	85%
Sembling and Indra. [79]	2025	Pre-trained and scratch-trained of ResNet18, VGG16, transfer learning, data augmentation	Private	7509 MRI images	Multi-class	This study outperformed scratch-trained and pre-trained of the models like ResNet18 to achieved best accuracy while VGG16 from scratch performed the worst.	97.43%,
Gencer [80]	2025	AlexNet, EfficientNetB0, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) for feature reduction	Figshare	3064 MRI images	Multi-class	This study proposed EfficientNetB0 and AlexNet which significantly outperformed especially when enhanced with PCA which reduced computational complexity while achieving high accuracy.	97.87%

5.3. Summary of the Comparative Analysis

From 2020 to 2025, research on brain tumour classification using MRI images has evolved rapidly. In the early years, most studies relied on pre-trained models like VGG16, ResNet, InceptionV3, and DenseNet, which performed very well when supported by proper preprocessing and data augmentation. Over time, however, researchers began developing custom lightweight CNNs and newer architectures such as EfficientNet that matched or even exceeded these pre-trained models, offering faster training and lower computational costs. A clear shift can also be seen toward hybrid approaches combining CNNs with traditional machine learning methods like SVM, KNN, and ensemble models to boost accuracy and make predictions more reliable. Throughout this period, techniques like data augmentation and cross-validation remained essential, helping models learn effectively from limited medical datasets and reducing overfitting. In recent years, attention has turned toward making these systems more efficient, interpretable, and

generalizable across different datasets. Models now increasingly incorporate explainable AI, Vision Transformers, and even quantum-inspired designs. Overall, the field has moved from basic CNNs to more intelligent, integrated, and clinically useful systems that better reflect the complexity of real-world medical imaging. The following subsections present a concise summary of the reviewed studies from multiple perspectives, including techniques used, dataset characteristics, classification types, performance trends, and key research advancements.

5.3.1 Chronological Overview (2020–2025)

Table 7 shows the evolution of CNN-based methods used in brain tumor detection and classification in MRI images in the research articles we have reviewed, published between 2020-2025. The table summarizes key developments and common research themes in each year, showing how the methods have evolved from basic CNN architectures and transfer learning to more advanced approaches such as hybrid, transformer-based, and quantum models.

Table 7. Summary of the commonly used Methods by year

Period	Key Developments	Common Themes
2020–2021 (Early CNN Era)	Custom CNNs, pre-trained VGG/ResNet models; heavy use of data augmentation and residual blocks.	Focus on basic architectures (VGG16, ResNet50), dataset augmentation, and cross-validation for robustness.
2022 (Hybridization & Optimization)	Emergence of hybrid CNN–KNN/SVM and feature fusion (PCA, PSO, ensemble).	Optimization of pre-trained models, feature selection, and ensemble methods improved generalization.
2023 (Transfer Learning & Hybrid Deep Models)	Integration of ResNet, DenseNet, and hybrid architectures (CNN–Autoencoder, CNN–SVM).	Emphasis on model efficiency, transfer learning, and ensemble approaches to reduce training cost.
2024 (Advanced Architectures & Transformers)	Use of YOLOv8, Vision Transformers (PBViT), hybrid 2D–3D CNNs, and domain adaptation (Neutrosophic Sets).	Diversification into object detection, segmentation (U-Net), and explainable AI models.
2025 (Quantum & Efficient Models)	Quantum CNNs, autoencoders (C-SAN), cascaded and multi-path CNNs, EfficientNet-based architectures.	Focus on computational efficiency, clinical interpretability, and cross-dataset generalization.

5.3.2 Techniques Used (Grouped Summary)

The table 8 provides a summarized view of the main CNN-based techniques applied for brain tumor detection and classification in MRI images studies from 2020 to 2025. It groups methods into key categories such as custom CNNs, pre-trained models, hybrid CNN-ML models, optimization techniques,

and novel architectures and indicates their frequency of use along with important insights from the literature. Also, the table highlights how research has progressed from conventional CNN-based models toward more efficient, hybrid, and transformer-based techniques that enhance performance, generalization, and interpretability.

Table 8. Summary of CNN Model Evolution

Technique Family	Example Models/Methods	Frequency	Key Insight
Custom CNNs	Simple CNN, Deep CNN, Optimized CNN	~20%	Foundation for most studies; highly dataset-dependent.
Pre-trained CNNs (Transfer Learning)	VGG16, ResNet50, DenseNet121, InceptionV3	~35%	Most widely adopted due to small datasets; improved convergence.
Hybrid Models (CNN + ML)	CNN-SVM, CNN-KNN, CNN-RF, CNN-Ensemble	~25%	Significantly improved accuracy and robustness by combining deep and shallow features.
Optimization & Feature Fusion	PCA, PSO, Ensemble Learning	~10%	Reduced redundancy and computational cost.
Transformer / Quantum / Novel Architectures	ViT, PBViT, Quantum CNN, C-SAN	~10% (2023–2025)	Represent the next generation, improving explainability and speed.

5.3.3 Dataset Trends

Table 9 provides an overview of the main datasets used for brain tumor detection and classification in reviewed articles between 2020 and 2025, and summarizes the data sources, frequency of use, size of the datasets, and key considerations for their applications. The table shows that most of the

researchers have used Kaggle for their studies around 200 to 40000 MRI images for both binary-class and multi-class classification of brain tumor. FigShare is the second most used source by researchers, and around 10% of studies have used BRATS, TCGA, also few studies used private dataset to validate the model's performance in real-world settings.

Table 9. Inventory of Datasets in Reviewed Articles

Source	Frequency	Typical Size	Remarks
Kaggle	Most frequent (\approx 60%)	200–40,000 MRI images	Used for both binary and multiclass tasks; extensive augmentation used to expand data.
Figshare	Moderate use (\approx 25%)	2,000–7,000	Often paired with SARTAJ/Br35H for cross-validation.
BRATS / TCGA / TCIA	\approx 10%	100–130,000	Used for clinical-grade segmentation and classification.
Private or Hospital Data	Few studies	400–7,000	Validates real-world generalizability.

5.3.4 Classification Types

Table 10 provides an overview of how brain tumor detection and classification tasks have been structured in recent studies. The table highlights the distinction between binary classification, which divides MRI images into tumor and non-tumor categories, and multiclass classification, which identifies specific

tumor types such as glioma, meningioma, and pituitary. The table also summarizes the number of studies, index models, and average accuracy obtained in each category, showing a clear shift in research direction toward multiclass classification after 2021 as datasets become larger and CNN architectures become more advanced.

Table 10. Classification Categories

Type	Studies	Representative Models	Avg. Accuracy
Binary-Class	16 studies	DenseNet121, VGG16, ResNet50	93.4%
Multi-Class	44 studies	InceptionV3, Hybrid CNN-SVM, Dense CNN, ViT-based models	95.9%

5.3.5 Accuracy Trends and Top Models

Table 11 provides a summary of the progress of model performance in brain tumor detection and classification reviewed studies from 2020 to 2025. The table displays the accuracy range, the highest accuracy recorded in each year, and the associated top

models or methods. Also, shows how the accuracy of the models has steadily improved over time, with the best results coming from hybrid and ensemble architectures that combine advanced CNN variants such as DenseNet, EfficientNet, and tuned VGG models.

Table 11. Evolution of Model Performance

Year	Accuracy Range	Top Accuracy (Study)	Key Model / Method
2020	91–96%	96.56% (Badža & Barjaktarović)	Deep CNN + subject-wise validation
2021	90–96%	96% (Qodri et al.)	ResNet50, VGG16 (Transfer Learning)
2022	92–97.8%	97.8% (Khan et al.)	23-layer CNN + Fine-tuned VGG16
2023	90–97.8%	97.87% (Gencer)	EfficientNetB0 + PCA
2024	75–97.85%	97.85% (Khan & Park)	Convolutional block-based CNN
2025	84–97.87%	97.87% (Gencer, EfficientNetB0)	EfficientNetB0 with PCA, cascaded CNNs

5.3.6 Summary Table by Year

Table 12 provides an overview of the annual progress of research in the field of brain tumor detection and classification from 2020 to 2025. The table plots the number of studies, their average accuracy, and key methodological advances achieved in each year. The

table highlights the continuous improvement and increasing diversification of techniques from the initial reliance on residual blocks and transfer learning to the use of hybrid CNN models, transformers, 3D CNNs, and quantum models in subsequent years, indicating the continuous evolution and refinement of deep learning methods in this field.

Table 12. Number of Reviewed Papers by Year

Year	No. of Studies	Avg. Accuracy	Key Advances
2020	5	94.6%	Residual blocks, data augmentation, subject-wise validation
2021	5	92.7%	Transfer learning (VGG/ResNet), efficiency emphasis

2022	7	95.9%	Hybrid CNN–KNN/SVM, ensemble, feature fusion
2023	10	95.8%	Dense CNNs, hybrid models, U-Net integration
2024	13	93.8%	YOLOv8, Vision Transformers, 3D CNNs, quantum approaches
2025	10	95.6%	EfficientNet, cascaded CNNs, autoencoders, generalization focus

5.4. General Challenges

This systematic literature review covering studies from 2020 to 2025 on brain tumor detection and classification using CNN-based techniques has identified several key challenges which shape this field. These challenges not only arise from algorithmic limitations but also from the complex MRI dataset acquisition, preprocessing, model evaluation, hardware requirement and others. One of the most fundamental problems is low quality of MRI images. MRI images are prone to various forms of noise and distortion caused by the physical operation of scanners or by patient movement during acquisition. These artifacts introduce unwanted variations that degrade images and impact on the model performance. Moreover, class imbalance biases models toward the dominant class and makes it difficult to achieve stable learning outcomes.

Challenges also extend deeply into the CNN model design itself. Most of the CNN architectures have performed well for binary-class classification but they often fail to generalize effectively when faced with multiple tumor types or mixed pathologies. Furthermore, multi-modal fusion of combining data from T1, T2, FLAIR, and T1c modalities remains an unsolved problem and the CNNs-based existing architectures rarely exploit all views simultaneously in a meaningful way. In other hand, few CNN-based models operate as fully automated, end-to-end systems capable of adapting to diverse imaging conditions or datasets without extensive manual intervention.

Dataset related issues are another major challenge in this field. While the Kaggle dataset provides a valuable benchmark, other publicly available datasets are scarce, inconsistent, or of limited quality. Private medical data often come in nonstandard formats, vary in labelling accuracy and contain significant noise. This absence of standardized datasets makes fair comparison across studies nearly impossible.

Preprocessing methods and Data augmentation offer some relief by artificially expanding limited datasets and noise reduction but there is no universally accepted augmentation technique tailored for MRI images and also poorly applied denoising or thresholding techniques degrade rather than improve image quality.

Finally, the computational and hardware requirements are the other big challenges for practical works, where researchers faced. CNN-based models require significant memory and processing capacity for training purpose. Researchers with limited resources often resort to shallow architectures. These shallow models train quickly but fail to capture deep hierarchical features, while deeper architectures extract the features deeply and achieve higher accuracy but need more time for training purpose and sometimes suffer from slow convergence and problems like gradient vanishing.

6. Conclusion and Future Direction

This paper presents the analyzing of recent CNN-based techniques used for brain tumor detection and classification in MRI images which are published in the last six years (2020-2025), we have used inclusion and exclusion criteria for selecting of articles from different databases like PubMed, ScienceDirect, Google Scholar, and IEEE Access and identified totally 310 articles. After screening and eligibility, 50 papers were selected for this study. After that, we have performed a literature review of all 50 articles and evaluated the effectiveness of CNN-based techniques for brain tumor detection and classification using MRI images. We have started our review with discussion studies publish in 2020 and end it to 2025 and detailed review of all articles performed with qualitative and quantitative analysis of the studies and compared the deep CNNs techniques to each other as a table, highlighted techniques, model used, datasets and their performance. After reviewing the related work some

limitations and challenges are found, and at the end we suggested some ideas like using pre-processing and noise-reduction for improve the quality of the MRI images, using hybrid CNN for multi-class classification and balancing the MRI dataset for better performance of deep learning models for brain tumor detection and classification.

There are some ideas for developing any deep learning models particularly CNNs-based techniques in the future for brain tumor detection and classification using MRI images, where in the existing studies the researchers faced. The most important thing is using advanced preprocessing and noise-reduction which improve the quality of MRI images. The other idea is designing and developing hybrid deep learning architectures which are capable to handling multi-classification with high performance. Also, CNNs that are trained on imbalanced datasets may be racist towards the majority class, which in turn means that the performance in the detection of the minority classes are not be as good as it should be. The use of techniques such as oversampling, under-sampling, or the implementation of weighted loss functions to solve the class imbalance problem, and it is very important issue for the performance of the model for tumor and non-tumor instances.

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